

PROCESS OPTIMIZATION OF PECTIN EXTRACTION FROM *OPUNTIA* SPP. AND CHARACTERIZATIONC. Rodrigues¹, A. A. A. Rheinboldt^{1,2}, V.G.L. Souza^{1,3}, I. Coelho⁴, M. Rashad⁵, L. Pari⁶, A. Outzourhit⁷, A.L. Fernando¹¹MEtRICs, Departamento de Ciências e Tecnologia da Biomassa (DCTB), NOVA SCHOOL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY | FCT NOVA, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Campus de Caparica, 2829-516, Caparica, Portugal; Tel. and fax: 351.21.2948543; e-mail: ala@fct.unl.pt²Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil³INL, International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory, Braga, Portugal⁴LAQV-REQUIMTE, Departamento de Química, NOVA SCHOOL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY | FCT NOVA, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Caparica, Portugal⁵City of Scientific Research and Technological Applications, Egypt⁶Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia agraria, Italy⁷Université Cadi Ayyad, Morocco

ABSTRACT: Cactus (*Opuntia* spp.) is considered a promising crop to surpass the climate change effects in agriculture as it is a xerophytic plant which is particularly adapted to arid lands (e.g. Mediterranean area, including North Africa) and severely degraded soils that are unsuitable for traditional crops. The mucilage from the palms of the plant (cladodes) is rich in polysaccharides (especially pectin) capable to form viscous solutions with promising applications in the food industry and as edible films and coatings. Once the cladodes are poorly utilized, and considered as a by-product, the aim of this work was to optimize an efficient and sustainable method to extract pectin from this biomass to be used as a biobased material in a circular economy approach. Moreover, application of the extracted pectin to substitute fossil based products, e.g. plastics in the food packaging, will contribute to accomplish the targets of the European Green Deal in terms of reducing fossil-based packaging waste and reducing dependence on non-renewable, unsustainable resources, helping to decarbonize the economy. Extraction processes follow the succeeding route: (1) removal of cladodes outer layers; (2) washing/cutting, (3) mix with solvent, (4) centrifugation; (5) precipitation with ethanol; (6) drying. To optimize the extraction process, different solvents were tested (water, citric acid and acetic acid), as also different extraction parameters (extraction temperature and time, pH, among others). Preliminary results indicate that a yield (in dry basis) ranging from 7 to 15 %, can be obtained by using the different solvents at 80 °C. Ultrasound combined with lower temperatures enhanced the extraction yield, improving the sustainability of the process. Based on the results obtained, it can be concluded that acidic solutions facilitate pectin extraction with a high esterification degree, rich in galacturonic acid units. Also, it can be concluded that the use of organic acids (e.g citric acid) avoids pectin depolymerization.

Keywords: *Opuntia* spp., biopolymers, biobased products, biobased economy, circular economy

1 INTRODUCTION

Opuntia spp is a perennial crop, native from Mexico, but currently spread all over the Globe, especially in South America and Mediterranean region [1-4]. It is a spiny succulent plant of the *Cactaceae* family, which is considered a promising crop to surpass the climate change effects in agriculture once it is a xerophytic plant, particularly adapted to arid lands and severely degraded soils that are unsuitable for traditional crops [5-7]. Its fruit, prickly pear, with an edible portion of 54%, is a food with nutraceutical and functional importance, widely used for human consumption. It is very rich in antioxidants that can be used as preservatives in foodstuff or, when incorporated into polymers can act as active ingredient in active packaging, enhancing the shelf life of food, like other antioxidants from other fruits and plants [8-17]. The vegetative part of the plant, constituted by cladodes, are essentially used as animal feed, despite their rich content in polysaccharide (pectin) that could be extracted and used in the food industry as additive or to produce edible films and coatings [18], [19]. The fruit is also very rich in betalains, which can be useful for the construction of bio-based sensors [20].

Pectin is a structural polysaccharide present in the cell wall of plants [21]. It is a polymer with high molecular weight, capable to form hydrogels, coatings and flexible thin films [18], [19]. Traditionally, commercial pectin are extracted from apples and citrus fruits [22]. However, other plants, such as *Opuntia ficus-indica*, can also be used as source of this valuable polysaccharide. Moreover,

the extraction from by-products of the cultivation and use of these cactus (i.e. from the fruit's peel or the cladodes discarded from the prune) represent itself as a green option, in line with the concept of circular bioeconomy, also already reported by other authors [23-26]. Due to the cactus mucilage positive characteristics, such as its film-forming capacity, biodegradability, and safety, it has shown to have remarkable potential to be used by the food industry as a natural biopolymer, as an alternative to the petroleum-based non-biodegradable polymer [27].

Yet, more studies in terms of mucilage extraction process are demanded to develop a more efficient and sustainable method of extraction.

This work was done in the scope of the ERANETMED project MediOpuntia, which aims to promote the plantation in large scale of cactus in marginal lands of Mediterranean countries (Portugal, Italy, Morocco and Egypt), with minimum pressure on available water resources. Moreover, the project aims to develop an integrated management package of inventive low-cost on-farm practices for producing cactus as well as adding value to the final product by introducing innovative manufacturing techniques to produce functional food and bio-based products from cactus seeds, stems and fruits. In the framework of the MediOpuntia project the aim of this work was to develop an efficient and sustainable method to extract the mucilage from the cladodes with characteristics suitable to be used as a bio-based film material or coating in the preservation of foodstuff in a circular economy approach (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Circular economy approach to use cactus in the preservation of foodstuff.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

Opuntia ficus-indica cladodes, used as the biomass in this work, were collected in April 2019 and kindly supplied by Pepe Aromas, Alentejo, Portugal.

2.1 Pectin extraction procedure

The extraction was carried out using cladodes and was performed in both outer (peel) and inner (pulp) layers in separated or combined mode using different extract solutions [28], namely: water and citric acid. Briefly, cladodes were cut, homogenized with the solvent in the proportion of 1:1 w/w and boiled for 20 min at 80°C in a water bath. The mixture was centrifuged, and the supernatant (viscous material) was precipitated with absolute ethanol (2:3 v/v) and kept overnight at 4°C. After precipitation, the samples were washed with 96% ethanol and filtered under vacuum conditions recovering the solid part. The samples were then dried at 45°C. The yield of extraction was expressed in % of mucilage of dry weight. Figure 2 shows the methodology used to extract pectin from the cladodes. Several parameters were studied in order to optimize the extraction yield, namely, pH, particle size, solid/liquid ratio, temperature, different extraction solutions, contact time and the use of other techniques that can promote the pectin extraction (e.g. ultrasound, microwave, PEF (Figure 3)).

The pectin extracted was characterized using ATR-FTIR and compared with commercial pectin.

Figure 2: Pectin extraction methodology

Figure 3: Parameters studied on the optimization of pectin extraction from cladodes.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The extraction was accomplished successfully using both extraction solutions. However, the extraction yield was superior when the citric acid solution was used (Figure 4). It is also noticeable, that the source of the biomass did not affect the extraction yield, but the peels have slightly more pectin than the pulp.

Figure 4: Pectin extraction yield.

The extraction method using acid solutions as extraction solutions with further alcoholic precipitation is commonly used on industrial scale to obtain pectin [9]. So, using acid solutions such as citric acid, to extract pectin from cladodes is a promising option. Superior extraction yields were obtained when high temperatures and low pH were applied on the extraction with acid solutions. This effect can be attributed to the hydrolysis of protopectin [29].

It was expected that the extraction yield in the pulp would be greater than from the peel, once the mucilaginous cells are more abundant in the parenchyma (related to the pulp) than the chlorenchyma (related to the peel) [30]. However, the opposite was found in our results, which is related with the extraction process. In fact, in the extraction, other components can be also extracted, such as some other fibers than pectin that are present in the peels. This may interfere in the results, by contributing to the amount extracted and precipitated. Different factors improved the extraction yield (to a maximum of 15 % dry matter basis): the extra method used (PEF, ultrasound, microwave), the conditions (low pH, high temperature), acidic solutions, which is in agreement with data presented in the literature [31].

In order to compare the pectin obtained with the commercial pectin, FTIR spectra was done from both materials (Figure 5). The peaks and the assignments found are depicted in Table I.

The peaks displayed for the extracted pectin from *Opuntia* are quite similar to those for commercial pectin, with differences that can be explained by the source of the biomass, extraction procedure, presence of some impurities. But, overall, the characteristic chemical groups related to the pectin are present confirming that the material obtained is indeed this valuable polymer.

Figure 5: FTIR of commercial pectin (A) and extracted from *Opuntia* (B).

Table I: Assignments of FTIR wavenumbers in the range 4000–400 cm^{-1} of *Opuntia* and commercial pectin from citric fruits.

FTIR wavenumber (cm^{-1})		Assignments [14]
<i>Opuntia</i> pectin	Commercial	
3451	3463	O-H
2962	2969	C-H
1736	1742	C=O from methylesterified
1583	1612	C=O from free carboxyl groups
600-1200	600-1200	Finger prints

4 CONCLUSIONS

Preliminary results indicate that a yield (in dry basis) ranging from 7 to 15 %, can be obtained by using the different extraction solutions at 80 °C. Ultrasound combined with lower temperatures enhanced the extraction yield, improving the sustainability of the

process. Based on the results obtained, it can be concluded that acidic solutions facilitate pectin extraction with a high esterification degree, rich in galacturonic acid units. Also, it can be concluded that the use of organic acids (e.g citric acid) avoids pectin depolymerization. Work is in progress to identify which extraction procedure simultaneously presents good yields and pectin with optimal characteristics for the production of biopolymers.

5 REFERENCES

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